

PROCESSING AND PROPERTIES OF RAPID CURE PREIMPREGNATED COMPOSITE SYSTEMS

James D. Holbery, Brian D. Flinn and Rajendra K. Bordia
Department of Materials Science and Engineering
Roberts Hall, FB-10
University of Washington, Seattle, WA 98105, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

A modified preimpregnated fiberglass epoxy composite system has been developed and tailored for the production of sporting goods. Utilizing latent cure agents, four systems were developed which met the process and design criterion set forth for this project. It was found that comparable mechanical and physical properties are obtained with these new systems as compared to two commercial epoxy prepreg systems and one epoxy-single combination catalyst "wet" lay-up composite system. Tests performed include Flexural Modulus, Flexural Strength, Short Beam Shear, Degree of Cure and Glass Transition Temperature using both a Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC) and Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA). Material processing, selection, and process design methodology are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The manufacture of fiber reinforced composite sporting goods is performed using a variety of processes and material combinations. Traditionally, most fiber reinforced composite sporting goods have been produced using "wet" hand lay-up techniques which may be labor intensive, produce significant amounts of waste material, and have final mechanical properties which may vary. Recently, companies have attempted to incorporate aerospace grade materials and processes into their production process to increase product quality, throughput, and to decrease the amount of waste material.

Many high glass transition glass and carbon fiber preimpregnated formulations have been developed for the aerospace industry[1]. However, these systems are typically designed to cure at 177°C in two hours, although aircraft repair and tooling formulates cure at lower temperatures and longer cycles[2]. Due to the ability to control resin content in the final product, ease of handling, and controllable material tack and drape[3], fibers preimpregnated with a catalyzed epoxide polymer are now being used for load-bearing structural applications in high end tennis rackets, fishing poles, and bicycles[4].

The aim of this project is to develop a preimpregnated modified epoxy fiberglass material which will cure in 10 minutes at 110°C. The requirement for the final product formulation is that the cured material exhibit mechanical properties equal to or greater than that of common wet resin systems and that the prepreg material form maintain at least a one week shelf life at room temperature without any significant degradation of mechanical properties. In addition, the prepreg is to be a hot melt system with no volatile producing solvents incorporated into the formulation.

MATERIALS AND PROCESSES

Materials selected for test and analysis are divided into three thermoset polymeric composite groups:

- Commercial Wet Resin
- Commercial Prepreg
- Formulated Experimental Prepreg

Each system was selected based on discussions with suppliers, sporting goods manufacturers, and the process requirements of the project. Test samples were cured in a heated platen press at a nominal pressure of 70 K Pascal (100 psi) heated to the prescribed temperature and held under pressure for the prescribed time duration. The ramp rate for heating and cooling was 40°C per minute.

COMMERCIAL WET RESIN

A two-part, epoxy resin system, representative of that used in sporting goods manufacture, was provided by Dow Chemical. The system selected was Dow DER 383 diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy resin having a weight per epoxide equivalent of 183. This was subsequently combined with a tetraethylenepentamine/triethylenetetramine hardener above the stoichiometric level. This level was used to meet the accelerated cure schedule and although not recommended by the manufacturer is used in practice by some producers of sporting goods.

Composite panels were produced from standard E-glass fibers (PPG Industries product designation 2016, TEX = 1984, yield = 250) treated with an epoxy specific silane based sizing. The unidirectional fibers were stitched parallel to one another with fiberglass thread of 0.10 mm diameter transverse to the unidirectional fiber direction and spaced at 1.25 cm intervals. The final weight of the uniformly stitched unidirectional fiber mat was 460 grams per square meter. The cross stitch thread is intended to act as a method of maintaining the fiber orientation of the unidirectional fibers during both the laminating and cure processes. It is believed that the contribution by the cross stitch thread to both mechanical properties and the failure mode of the laminate is minimal. The panels were cured between platens heated to 110°C for 10 minutes using 2.5 mm aluminum stops to control laminate thickness.

COMMERCIAL PREPREG

The commercial prepreg materials selected are the Ciba NTT5 and Hexcel HX1588. Both of these are commercially available, although the Hexcel system at the time of test was an experimental product. Both are solvent based systems and at the time of this writing, the Ciba NTT5 system is only produced in Austria. The prepreg fiberglass cloth was a 7781 style E-glass bi-axial weave which was the only material form available from each supplier at the time of investigation. The systems selected are based on accelerated cure schedules recommended by the manufacturers as appropriate for this program.

Two cure schedules were selected, and are as follows:

- (A) 20 minutes at 102°C
- (B) 30 minutes at 127°C

Each of these cure schedules are considered to be below the time and temperature necessary to produce full cure. It is noted that the requirements of this project are not met by either of these cure profiles and that neither cure schedule maintains one hour at 121°C as is the recommended practice by each manufacturer. Laminates were manufactured by hand lay-up on aluminum caul sheets, cured between heated platens using 2.5 mm aluminum stops to control laminate thickness.

EXPERIMENTAL PREPREG

The experimental systems developed are all based on using a standard DGEBA epoxide backbone combined with latent cure agents and accelerators. The primary cure agents used were aliphatic and modified amines, dicyandiamide and dihydrazide latent cure agents, and urea accelerators. No solvents were used for dilution. Experimental resin systems were used to prepreg E-glass fiber supplied by PPG Industries with an epoxy compatible silane sizing. The material was produced on a laboratory scale prepreg machine equipped with three separate heat zones to control the B-stage process. Plies of each material system were cut to size and processed using the same procedure as described above for the previous material systems. Each system was cured for 10 minutes at 110°C under the prescribed pressure.

PHYSICAL CHARACTERIZATION

Although full physical and cure characterization will be reported in forthcoming papers, the material glass transition temperature and degree of cure are reported. Samples of each material were obtained from cured panels and transitions identified with a Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC). In addition, simulated cure cycles were run on the DSC and upon reheat transition temperatures were compared to those obtained from the heated platen cured panels.

The instrument used to measure glass transition temperature (T_g) is the Perkin-Elmer DSC Model 7. These tests were conducted ICI/Fiberite Test Method D6. Samples were scanned at 10°C/min. from 30°C to 200°C and the exotherm generated by the heat of reaction was monitored with the DSC. After numerous trial runs and a review of the literature [6], this scan rate was selected. An onset temperature was calculated from the inflection point to the baseline and recording the temperature at the intersection of these two lines. Confirming measurements were produced on a Perkin Elmer Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA). The final extent of cure (%) of each material system was calculated using the DSC data by measuring the residual heat of reaction as follows in Equation (1):

$$\text{Extent of Cure (\%)} = \frac{\Delta H_o - \Delta H_p}{\Delta H_o} \cdot (100) \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_o is the heat of reactions of material fully cured at 180°C and ΔH_p is the heat of reaction of the material after run through the cure cycle described previously. Table 1 lists the glass transition temperatures (T_g) and degree of cure of each of material system.

Table 1. Composite T_g & % Cure

<u>Sample</u>	<u>System</u>	<u>T_g(°C)</u>	<u>% Cure</u>
1	"Wet" System (110°C/10 min.)	139	96.7
2	Ciba NTT5(Cure A)	121	78.4
3	Ciba NTT5(Cure B)	129	92.1
4	Hexcel HX1588(Cure A)	116	67.8
5	Hexcel HX1588(Cure B)	127	89.6
6	Composite Formulation 1(110°C/10 min.)	126	91.2
7	Composite Formulation 2(110°C/10 min.)	99	94.1
8	Composite Formulation 3(110°C/10 min.)	127	90.8
9	Composite Formulation 4(110°C/10 min.)	136	87.5

The data reported above indicates that the "wet" Dow 383/DEH 78 system T_g is near its maximum as it is 96.7% cured, or near full cure. The commercial prepreg system data indicates that the higher the cure temperature and the longer the cure cycle, the greater the extent of cure and consequently the higher the glass transition temperature. Due to the chemical differences in the cure agents used in the four in-house formulations, each system exhibits a unique behavior. For example, Formulation 2 has the highest percent cure when held at 110°C for 10 minutes but has the lowest T_g. Formulation 4, on the other hand, has the lowest percent cure but the highest T_g for the same cure cycle. While the glass transition temperatures of all formulations are

deemed acceptable for the final application, it has been reported that a conversion factor of at least 90% is desired to insure long term stability for amine-epoxy reactions[7].

MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION

The mechanical characterization of the composite systems outlined above are divided into two sections. First, an evaluation of the commercial composite systems is provided followed by a section addressing the properties of the four experimental formulations developed. Finally, a comparison is made of the commercial and formulated systems to the cured wet resin composite properties. Flexural strength and flexural modulus tests were performed per ASTM D790, Method 1, Procedure A, short beam shear per ASTM D 2344 and the fiber volume determined per ASTM D 2734.

Due to different processing techniques and process variability, the volume fraction of fibers in the composites were different. The variation was nominally between 42 to 46%. In an effort to accurately compare the short beam shear strength data of one material system to another, the as measured data has been corrected to calculated value for 55% fiber volume fraction. This transformation is accomplished by incorporating the stress concentration factor as follows in Equation (2):

$$\sigma_{Measured}(s_{Vf Actual}) = \sigma_{Vf @ 55\%}(s_{Vf @ 55\%}) \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_{Measured}$ is the measured short beam shear strength, $s_{Vf Actual}$ is the stress concentration factor calculated at the measured fiber volume, and $s_{Vf @ 55\%}$ is the stress concentration factor calculated at 55% fiber volume. Rearranging Equation (2), $\sigma_{Vf @ 55\%}$, the shear strength at 55% fiber volume, is given by:

$$\sigma_{Vf @ 55\%} = \frac{\sigma_{Measured}(s_{Vf Actual})}{s_{Vf @ 55\%}} \quad (3)$$

where the stress concentration s_{Vf} is defined as follows:

$$s_{Vf} = \frac{1 - Vf}{1 - \left(\frac{4 \cdot Vf}{\pi}\right)^{0.5}} \quad (4)$$

This equation holds for $\frac{E_m}{E_f} \ll 1$. Substituting the measured fiber volume Vf into Equation (4), the stress concentration is computed for the specific measured fiber volume. Using Equation (4), the computed stress concentration at 55% fiber volume is 2.758. This method was utilized for determining the short beam shear data reported in the plots throughout this manuscript. In addition, the fiber dominated mechanical properties (e.g. flexural modulus and flexural strength) were also calculated for $V_f = 55\%$ using Eq. (5):

$$\text{Properties for } V_f @ 0.55 = \frac{\text{Measured Properties}}{V_f Actual} \cdot 0.55 \quad (5)$$

COMMERCIAL PREPREG PROPERTIES

The commercial systems tested were cured as described in the previous section. The laminates were then machined and samples from these laminates were used for both mechanical and physical property development. Trends were observed in the mechanical properties as a function of degree of cure, void volume, and glass transition temperatures. The flexural modulus data provided below in Fig. 1 indicates that the flexural modulus for each system does not increase appreciably as a function of the two cure cycles used, although the data scatter decreased

significantly for the Ciba system for Cure Schedule B. Data has been calculated for 55% fiber volume using Eq. (5)

Figure 1. Flexural Modulus (computed using Eq. 5) vs. Tg: Commercial Systems

The cure schedule did have a dramatic effect on the short beam shear strength. This is to be expected as this property is resin dominated: as the degree of cure and glass transition temperature increase with both the duration and temperature of cure, the shear strength of the laminate should increase accordingly. Fig. 2 depicts the short beam shear strength values computed for 55% fiber volume (using Eqs. 3 and 4) as a function of degree of cure.

Figure 2. Short Beam Shear Strength (computed using Eqs. 3 & 4) vs. Tg: Commercial Systems

Given the manufacturer recommended cure temperature and cure duration, the cure schedules selected are closer to that recommended by Ciba than the schedule recommended by Hexcel. This is perhaps the reason for the higher mechanical values and higher degree of cure for the Ciba material as compared to the Hexcel material.

EXPERIMENTAL PREPREG PROPERTIES

The properties of four experimental prepregs are illustrated below. Multiple laminates of each experimental formulation were manufactured and tested as described in the previous section. Each data point presented represents the average of at least three samples. Glass transitions were measured on each specimen sampling. Interpretation of the graphs, such as the flexural modulus

as a function of glass transition in Fig. 3, should be evaluated in terms of the entire sampling group as opposed to each point.

Figure 3. Flexural Modulus(computed using Eq. 5) vs. T_g: Experimental Formulations

Although the above plot indicates that flexural modulus increases with glass transition temperature, short beam shear strength, in general, increases as a function of the percent cure. Short beam shear is a resin dominated property and the overall positive trend in shear strength reflects the resin modulus increasing as a function of percent cure. Fig. 4 a plot of short beam shear as a function of degree of cure, illustrates this point.

Figure 4. Short Beam Shear Strength(computed using Eqs. 3 & 4)vs. Degree of Cure: Experimental Systems

The effect of material storage at room temperature is of concern in the production environment. One of the requirements of the project is that there should be very little degradation in resin dominated properties in one week time at room temperature. Given that short beam shear is one of the better tests of resin integrity provided bonding to the fiber is insured, tests were conducted on prepreg laminates manufactured one day after prepreg preparation and compared to laminates made from one week old prepreg. Figure 5 plots short beam shear results as a function of out time at room temperature.

Figure 5. Short Beam Shear Strength (computed using Eq. 3 & 4) vs. Flexural Modulus: Experimental Systems

Figure 5 indicates that short beam shear values degrade between 0-5% in all of the experimental prepreg composite systems. Further investigation of this phenomena has been conducted and will be reported in subsequent publications.

Finally, it is noted that while the mechanical and physical performance are outlined in this document, perhaps the greatest potential benefit to the end user now using a wet lay-up process is the potential savings realized during the manufacturing process and the optimized utilization of material resources. At this time, manufacturing processes which produce significant amounts of waste materials are under pressure to reduce waste while maintaining performance levels. The incorporation of a prepreg material to replace wet resins in a manufacturing process would better utilize resources while producing an accurate, reproducible process and end product. Reducing waste materials would result in benefits to the manufacturer such as material, waste disposal, and labor cost savings.

CONCLUSIONS

Four experimental prepreps have been manufactured and characterized which cure to 87.5% or above under the accelerated cure condition of 10 minutes at 110°C. Modified amines combined with latent cure agents have been used to develop four hot melt prepreg material systems which have been shown to crosslink a DGEBA epoxy matrix and have been shown not to degrade significantly due to one week of exposure at room temperature.

The following is a summary of the results presented:

- Extent of cure of the commercial systems tested increases with duration and cure temperature. The maximum extent of cure produced from a cure cycle of 30 minutes at 127°C for the Hexcel HX1558 and Ciba NTT5 was 89.6% and 92.1%, respectively.
- Commercial prepreg test results indicate flexural modulus data scatter decreases as glass transition temperature increases and short beam shear strength increases as extent of cure and Tg increase.
- Mechanical testing of the experimental systems indicates there is very little correlation between flexural modulus and Tg at the prescribed cure cycle. Short beam shear strength results are shown to increase as a function of degree of cure.
- The short beam shear strength of experimental prepreps stored for one week at room temperature and humidity were not adversely effected.

In an effort to compare the relative material mechanical performance of the systems tested, a direct comparison of the mechanical properties of each system is depicted and plotted. Although this is not a comparison of design allowables, this illustrates the mechanical performance of each system relative to the others. Figure 6 is a plot of the Flexural Modulus vs. Flexural Strength for the Wet Resin composite, Experimental Prepregs 1 and 2, and the Hexcel 1558 and Ciba NTT5 cured under Schedule B conditions.

Figure 6. Flexural Modulus vs. Flexural Strength(both computed using Eq. 5)

REFERENCES

1. W.I. Lee, A.C. Loos, and G.S. Springer, *J. Comp. Matr.*, **16**, 510 (1982).
2. F. Lee, S. Brinkerhoff, and S. McKinney, *35th SAMPE Symposium, May 2-5, 2202-2215*, (1990).
3. K.J. Ahn and J.C. Seferis, Prepreg Processing Science and Engineering, *Polymer Engineering and Science, September, Vol. 33, No. 18, 1177-1188* (1993).
4. S.C. Levin, Composites and Bicycles: Market Diversification in Action. *38th SAMPE Symposium, May 10-13, 1470-1480*, (1993).
5. ICI Fiberite, Materials Handbook.
6. N.L. Hancox, The Influence of Processing on an Anhydride Cured Epoxide Resin, *SAMPE Quarterly, Vol. 18, No. 2, 1-6*, 1987.
7. P.L. Wiggins, Curing Acceleration of a Hindered Aromatic Diamine-Epoxy System, *SAMPE Quarterly, Vol. 18, No. 1, 15-21*, 1986.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge financial support for this research from Anthony Industries, the Washington Technology Center and the National Science Foundation of the United States (grant No. DMR-NYI 9257027).